

Effects of Class Repetition on Pupils' Academic Performance in Public Primary Schools in Alego Usonga Sub-County, Kenya

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Abstract: Repetition has severe negative consequences to both the individuals and society in terms of economic, social, political and psychological dimensions. Alego Usonga Sub County, Siaya County has a high repetition rate of 7.10% against 1% nationally. The purpose of the study was to establish effect of class repetition on pupils' academic performance in primary schools in Kenya, and particularly to: examine how class repetition affects learner academic achievements. The high repetition rate was argued to improve academic performance by exposing low performing students to additional teaching time and allowing them to catch up on the curriculum and content of teaching. Equally repetition on the other side was argued to be counterproductive on student long term academic achievements with retained students falling further and further behind promoted peers and sometimes leading to drop outs. Conceptual framework was used in the study to help focus on the effects of repetition on pupils academic performance in primary schools in the Alego Usonga Sub County. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The study was carried out in public primary schools in Alego Usonga Sub County, Siaya County, Kenya. The population of the study comprised of 139 class teachers, 139 primary head teachers, Sub County Director of Education (SCDE), 7 Curriculum Support Officers (CSOs) and 695 repeaters. The study adopted simple random sampling technique and applied the rule of thumb to select 28 public primary schools to form part of the sample and to select 139 repeaters from the population of 695 repeaters to form the sample. Stratified random sampling was then used to select 28 head teachers, 28 class teachers, while saturated sampling was used to allow all the CSOs and SCDE to form part of the study. The instruments of data collections were questionnaires, documents analysis and interview schedules. This resulted in the development of a correlation coefficient of 0.857, which validated the reliability of the questionnaires after simultaneously giving two separate but alternative versions of questionnaires designed to sample the same content to respondents in pilot schools. Validity of the instruments were ascertained by the Supervisor from the Department of educational foundations of Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology. Quantitative data collected using close ended items in the Questionnaires, were analyzed using descriptive statistics like frequencies and percentages while qualitative data were analyzed as themes and Sub themes. The findings were presented in form of tables and graphs. The study revealed that repetition was frequent in seventh grade and had a detrimental impact on the academic performance of elementary school students. Also, it established that the primary effects of class repetition on students are stigmatization, low self-esteem, school dropouts, overage learners, low learning achievements, and a higher teacher-to-student ratio, which contributed to

constraints on school learning resources that negatively impacted on students' academic performance. Based on the study findings, the following were recommended: that the Government should put on more effort on the monitoring of educational quality through Sub County Quality Assurance and Standards Officer (SCQASO) and Curriculum Support Officers (CSOs) to check on the level of enforcement of the Government policy on repetition, the Teachers' Service Commission should redistribute teachers based on enrollment in schools to address the high teacher pupil ratio, the Government should prioritize the improvement of basic learning institution resources including physical infrastructure, desks, textbooks and lunch programs. confidence in learners and to encourage learners to love school and learning. The study was useful as it provided information to the Sub County Education office, parents, teachers and other stakeholders on effects of repetitions in primary schools in the Sub County.

Keywords: Repetition, Academic Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) defines education as a system of planned and continuous instruction aiming to impart a mix of information, skills, and understanding that is applicable to all aspects of life (UNESCO, 2018). Education is the process of gaining or transferring knowledge, enhancing cognitive abilities, and preparing one's mind for the challenges of human existence. Education comprises imparting or gaining specific knowledge and abilities; yet, as indicated by the definition of education, students have not been able to obtain the required knowledge and skills due to waste in the form of repeats and dropouts (UNESCO, 2021).

According to (UNESCO, 2012), Grade repetition is common practice worldwide and is one of the worst forms of wastage in schools. High rates of grade retention, early school dropout, and low educational attainment had impeded progress that could have been made and will still continue to pose significant challenges in the future. A study in 2010 established that 32.2 million elementary school pupils repeated a grade while 31.2 million dropped out of school prior to finishing their final grade. Pupils who were older than their grade level, chiefly attributed to by late entry or repetition were more vulnerable to school dropout. The likelihood of girls enrolling in elementary schools was determined to be lower than that of boys, whereas boys were more likely to repeat grades than girls.

In Latin America, grade repetition is prevalent in both elementary and secondary schools (Ward & Wilson, 2018). Primary schools in Brazil, for example, the rate of repetition approaches 20%. Nicaragua, Peru, and Uruguay follow suit with between 8% and 10% repetition rates (Shrestha et al., 2019). In lower secondary education, Brazil (17%) has the highest repetition rate, followed by Uruguay (12%). In Germany and Italy, two developed countries where repetition occurs, lower secondary education repetition rates range between 2% and 3% (Blackman, 2022). The United States likely stands apart from other developed nations. CPS estimates for the 1990s indicate that approximately 12% of 12–15-year-olds have repeated at least one grade, although the US Department of Education does not provide official figures on repetition (M.-Y. Yang et al., 2018).

South and Western Asia have the second-highest proportion of primary repeaters. Between 2000 and 2010, the total population of primary school repeaters increased by 18 percent, from 7.7 million to 9.1 million while the enrolment of pupils in primary schools fluctuated, indicating an increment of averagely 18 percent over this period. Currently, 9 percent of pupils reported to repeat primary schools come from the Arab states. This however indicates an increase of number of repeaters when compared to the 7% (2.9 million) primary school repeaters in 2010 from the 41.7 million enrolments. The same study pointed out that in 2010, 9% of primary school repeaters came from the East Asia and Pacific region. Central Asia, Central and Eastern Europe, North America and Western Europe on the other hand were identified to contribute 2% of world's primary repeaters. The global repetition rate for lower secondary schools was established to have increased from 13.8 million to 14.1 million. Latin America and Caribbean, South and West Asia, and Sub-Saharan Africa were host to 70 % global lower secondary repeaters in 2010 (UNESCO, 2012).

UNESCO (2004) reports that 6.0% of primary school children globally repeat a grade. While the West and Central Africa have the greatest secondary school repetition rates (18.8%), the Middle East and North Africa have the highest rates of repetition (12%), and Eastern and Southern Africa have the highest rates of repetition (12.3%), the poll agrees that Sub-

Saharan Africa has the biggest percentage of primary education repeaters (11.4million) in 2010. The absolute number of repeaters has increased by 16% over the past decade, primarily due to a sharp rise in primary enrollment, which increased by 53% over the countries, with the highest rate being in Sub-Saharan African countries, where each year approximately 22% of primary students and 21% of secondary students repeated their grade, with the situation being worse in secondary schools in Congo (30.8%) and Algeria (27.2%)(Zapp, 2021).

Southern and Eastern Africa consortium for monitoring education quality (SACMEQ) statistics revealed that grade retention is reported by students in Mauritius, Seychelles, and Zimbabwe, despite their automatic promotion policies for primary education (Hungu, 2011). More than twenty percent of students questioned in Mauritius and Zimbabwe, for instance, reported having repeated at least one grade level. Burundi, Central African Republic, Congo, Lesotho, Namibia, and Togo have significant repetition rates across all grade levels, ranging from 10% to 49% and fluctuating between grade levels. The variations may be caused by a mixture of circumstances, including a significant number of underage or overaged children, a lack of accessible spaces in specific grade levels, and the usage of national examinations that restrict access to education. After taking certificate examinations, nearly one-third and fifty percent of students in Burkina Faso repeat the final grade of primary and lower secondary school, respectively. In some countries, where there are insufficient school seats, national examinations are frequently used to limit entry into educational programs(Njeng’ere, 2014).

According to (Onyango, 2020), the chief sources of internal inefficiency as a determinant of academic performance in Kenyan primary schools are student dropout and repetition. The study suggests that drop out and repetition rates are higher in upper classes, namely standards five to eight, with 10% of pupils from each class failing to move on to the next every year. (Gathura et al., 2021) observed that three million pupils, a third of the total population, repeat classes every year, with some being multiple repeaters, denying pupils the ideal age of 13–14 at class eight. Gathura further notes that repetition, though officially outlawed, remains a big problem in the country’s education system and is one major cause of high dropout, overage students, and poor grades. Siaya District Development report (2008-2012), indicated that Alego Usonga Sub County education sector is faced with drop out of students from schools and has reported high cases of repetition and non-completion. The Sub County Education management information system reports (2020) revealed that even though repetition is outlawed in the country the Sub County continues to receive cases of repetition across most schools. The report further explains that the trend manifests more at the apex of each cycle and attributes this to mean score attainment for purposes of school ranking.

Table 1: Repetition Rates for primary schools in Alego Usonga Sub County (2019-2020)

Year	Enrollment	Repetition	% repetition
2018	55396	3014	5.44%
2019	56429	4369	7.745%
2020	58021	4936	8.50%
Total	169846	12072	7.10%

Source: Siaya District Emis Report December 2020

Table 1 demonstrates that Alego Usonga Sub County's primary education has internal efficiency issues, which have led to an increase in instances of repetition-based wastage. The percentage of repetition increased from 3014 students (5.44%) in 2018 to 4936 students (8.50%) in 2020. In the past three years, the number of repetition cases in Alego Usonga Sub County had increased by about double. As shown in Table 1, the prevalence of repetition in Alego Usonga Sub County merits attention; hence, this study is in part a response to this.

Since the reintroduction of free primary education in 2003, Kenya has had a high enrollment rate of 84.9%. However, class repetition persists in Kenya's public elementary schools despite the 2013 prohibition on the practice by the Ministry of Education (J. A. Orodho et al., 2013). According to the Siaya District Development plan (2008-2012), from 2006 to 2007, the primary level completion percentage dropped significantly from 81.8% to 74.2%. While the wastage rate nationally ranges from 0.3% for repeaters, 1.0% to 3.9% for drop outs, in Alego Usonga Sub- County repetition rate was 4.2 % in the year 2006. By December 2014 repetition rate in the Sub County stood at 4.99% almost doubling in span of just a few years. (District Education Office Emis report, 2012-2014). The almost doubled rate of repetition of learners in the Sub County poses a great educational challenge to the society, the effects of this therefore deserve investigation.

Despite the increased percentage of class repetition, little research has been conducted on the impact grade repetition poses on the academic performance of learners in primary schools. Most studies have focused on quantitative studies on class repetition causes on the pupil (Plano Clark et al., 2008). Class repetition is a contemporary Education reform concern (Ndaruhutse et al., 2008). However, less consideration has been given to the effects of class repetition on learners' academic performance in public primary school education that can be adopted in schools. The purpose of the study was to establish effect of repetition on pupil's academic performance of pupils in primary school in Alego Usonga Sub County. The research was motivated by the following objective: To examine how class repetition affects learner academic achievements, a case of Alego Usonga Sub County. The study sought answers to the following research question: How does repetition affect learner academic achievements.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive survey approach to investigate the effects of grade repetition on primary school students' academic achievement in Alego Usonga Sub County. According to (Ngari, 2020), the design is suitable for data collection, summarization, presentation, and interpretation. (J. A. Orodho, 2009) agrees that descriptive survey research designs are employed in preliminary studies to enable researchers to collect, summarize, present, and interpret data for the purpose of elucidation. The research was conducted in public elementary schools in the Alego Usonga Sub County. The Sub County is located in Kenya's Siaya County. Bondo Sub County lies to the south, Bunyala Sub County to the north, Emuhaya and Butere Sub Counties to the north-east, and Kisumu West Sub County to the south-east form its borders. The Sub County encompasses a total area of 598.6km² and has a population of 218,367, of whom 140,674 are of school-age (6-13 years) (Republic of Kenya, 2009). This sub-county was appropriate for this study due to poor academic performance and high number of repeat cases in primary schools located within the subcounty.

A researcher's target population consists of any actual or fictitious individuals, events, or goals that share enough similarities for the researcher to extrapolate their findings to them (A. G. Mugenda, 2008). Alego Usonga There are 139 primary schools in the Sub County, so the sample included 139 headteachers, 139 class teachers, 695 students who had previously repeated a grade, the Sub County Director of Education, and 7 Curriculum Support Officers (CSOs). Therefore, the total number of participants in the study was 981. A sample is defined as a selection from a larger population (Kaliannan & Chandran, 2012). Therefore, the sample was utilized to generalize the investigated characteristics to the entire population. The research used a simple random sampling method, following the rule of thumb recommended by (Mills & Gay, 2019), which recommends taking a 10% sample from a large population and a 20% sample from a small population. Twenty percent of the population, or 139 schools, was randomly selected, yielding 28 schools. As further defined by (Burke, 2019), a random sample is one in which each member of the study's population is selected with a probability proportional to their representation in the sample.

The study utilized stratified random sampling to select 28 head teachers, 28 class teachers, and 139 repeaters, i.e., those who did not require replacement of the item drawn. The primary benefit of this method is that it ensures the sample is representative of the population of interest, which in turn guarantees that statistical inferences are reliable. Saturated sampling was utilized to include all seven CSOs and the Sub County Director of Education in the study. According to (Mills & Gay, 2019), the target population should be adequately represented in educational research. The study sample is displayed in the table that follows.

Table 2: Sampling matrix

DESCRIPTION	POPULATION	SAMPLE SIZE
SCDE	1	1
Head teacher	139	28
Class teacher	139	28
Repeaters	695	139
CSOs	7	7
Total	981	203

The sample frame shows a total population of 981 and the sample population proportion of 203; 20.6%. The investigation came to the conclusion that the population size affected how closely the data matched that of the population. Obtaining precise estimates of population values necessitates a sufficiently high sample size, as explained by (A. G. Mugenda, 2008),

who also stresses the importance of a large sample size. The data was gathered using questionnaires, for which a standard list of questions pertinent to the investigation was compiled (Saleem, 2009). There was one for each principal of the schools under investigation, as well as separate forms for each class teacher and the Sub-County Education Officer. There were three distinct types of structured questionnaire, including closed-ended and open-ended questions. (Geoffrey E. Mills, 2016) asserts that questionnaires allow respondents to openly share their thoughts, ideas, and opinions. (Taylor, 2008) argues that questionnaires have the benefit of being simple and a suitable method for collecting data from a large number of respondents. In order to discover the attitudes and opinions of individuals. A schedule of interviews was used to gather information from the Head teachers, SCDE, and CSOs.

A reliable instrument is one that consistently produces the same results. According to (A. G. Mugenda, 2008), dependability is defined as the consistency with which a given measuring process yields results in excess of the precision with which the underlying concept is measured by the instrument. To ensure the highest degree of accuracy, pilot research was undertaken at five schools outside of the final sample. As a part of the pilot study, we used the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of internal consistency, an established method for gauging reliability.

$$\text{Alpha} = \frac{Nr}{1+r(N-1)}$$

Where: r is the mean inter item correlation, and

N =number of items in the scale.

Due to the large scale in the items the researcher used SPSS Version 23 to derive the inter item correlation. Two different but alternative forms of the questionnaires constructed to sample the same content to the respondents in pilot schools at the same time was administered. Once the inter item correlation matrix was generated, they were summed up to estimate the mean correlation. For example: if the average inters item correlation of a scale that comprises six items was 0.5, then the alpha for the scale would be $6(.5) / (1+.5(6-1))$, which was 0.857.

The alpha value was thought to be a conservative measure of reliability. Its intended purpose is to provide an assessment of the validity of scales that contain only binary-scored items. When the coefficient of consistency between items on a scale is high, it indicates that those items are significantly correlated with one another, and vice versa (A. G. Mugenda, 2008). This method needed a single administration and offered a unique, quantitative measure of an instrument's internal consistency. This enabled the researcher discover the challenges the respondents were likely to encounter on the collection instruments employed. The pilot study also provided opportunity to predict how the items in the questionnaire were to be interpreted and the amount of time to be spent in answering the questions.

Validity refers to the extent to which the results derived from the analysis of the data accurately represent the phenomenon being investigated. According to (A. G. Mugenda, 2008), validity is the precision and significance of conclusions drawn from research results. There are three varieties of validity: face validity, content validity, and construct validity. Face validity denotes the probability that a question will be misunderstood or misinterpreted (Wilkenson, 1991). It was determined through pilot testing which items might be misunderstood or misinterpreted, thereby increasing the likelihood of face validity. Those items that required modification were modified accordingly. Content validity refers to whether or not the instrument adequately addresses the topic. My supervisor, who is well-versed in research, was consulted in order to guarantee that the instruments pass the content validity test.

The quantitative data gathered from questionnaires were analyzed using a variety of statistical methods, such as measures of central tendency and dispersion. Simple descriptive statistics were applied to quantitative data for analysis. Included in the statistics to be employed were frequency counts, means, tables, graphs, and percentages. The qualitative information gleaned from interview guides will be analyzed in real time, as overarching themes and smaller, more specific ones become clear. (Gray, 2013) remarked that qualitative data provides rich descriptions and explanations that demonstrate the chronological progression of events, as well as frequently leading to random findings.

The primary quantitative data collected in the field were first edited to eliminate glaring errors and identify questionnaires that were incomplete. Coding was performed to facilitate data analysis. Various measures of central tendencies, such as frequencies and percentages, were used to report the data (J. A. Orodho, 2009). Narratives and direct quotes from participants were used to illustrate how qualitative data from in-depth interviews and free-form questions were analyzed

thematically to meet the study's aims. According to (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Creswell, 2002) thematic analysis is a technique for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) in data. The data were then interpreted based on the emerging themes.

Ethics in research focuses on values, safety and privacy of those engaged in research exercise. Application of ethical standards from planning, data collection, analysis and dissemination of the results were enhanced. On the relationship between the research execution and the respondents, the researcher ensured that they freely give informed consent, that is, the researcher explained as clearly as possible the purpose of the study, the implications of their participation in the study and issues of confidentiality. The researcher ensured that she aims at doing the study within the University guidelines to achieve quality and besides acknowledging sources of academic works that are not her own.

3. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Effects of Repetition on Learner Academic Achievement in Public Primary Schools in Alego Usonga Sub County

Head teachers, class teachers, students, the Subcounty director of education, and Curriculum Support Officers were all asked to describe the impact of class repetition on the academic attainment of students. It was requested that the key informants comment on the consequences of repetition in primary schools. This was done in an effort to give policy recommendations on how to reduce waste in the primary education cycle, hence enhancing internal school efficiency. This was important because the purpose of the research was to find out how often students in Alego Usonga Sub County's public primary schools had to repeat a class in order to perform exam. Students' academic performance in public primary schools in Alego Usonga Sub County was affected by the following factors, as reported by respondents. Table 3 displays the variables.

Table 3: effects of repetition on academic performance in public primary schools in Alego Usonga Sub County.

Effects of repetition	Head teacher.	Percentages of head teachers	Class teacher.	Percentage of class teachers	CSOs	Percentage of CSOs
Suicide	25	100%	26	100%	3	42.85%
Loss of self esteem	25	100%	26	100%	7	100%
Stigma	25	100%	26	100%	7	100%
Over age learners.	18	72%	15	57%	–	–
Drugs and substance abuse.	8	32%	13	50%	2	28.5%
Class congestion	24	96%	22	84.6%	–	–
High teacher pupil ratio	25	100%	24	92.3%	–	–

The importance of this data to the study was to establish the effects of class repetition on learner academic achievement in Alego Usonga Sub County primary schools. Table 3 shows that loss of self-esteem and stigma were listed by all respondents (head teachers, class teachers and CSOs) to be effects of repetition on academic performance. Suicide was listed by all head teachers and class teachers; noticeably only 3 (42%) CSOs indicated suicide to be effect of repetition on academic performance of pupils in Alego Usonga Sub County. Other factors that were also listed to be effects of repetition were drugs and substance abuse, over age learners, class congestion and high teacher pupil ratio. It should also be noted that while head teachers and class teachers agreed on high teacher to student ratio to be an effect of repetition on learner's academic performance. All CSOs noted that teachers use poor delivery techniques to cover the syllabus hence causing repetition.

Education level of family members was also mentioned by nearly all respondents; only one headteacher, four teachers, and one CSO did not cite it as a reason of recurrence. The educational level of the family influences a child's participation in school, resulting in a lack of enthusiasm on the part of the student and the teacher, which leads to poor performance and repetition. As this is a quantitative study, a qualitative analysis was also undertaken to determine the performance of the students after repetition in accordance with the cause, and the results were identical to those of the quantitative analysis. As indicated by the comments of the majority of headteachers, inadequate teachers, malnutrition, inadequacy of physical facilities, large amount of material to be taught, failure to take tests, learner absenteeism, and poor performance on exams

were the leading causes of repetition. the family's degree of education, adolescent pregnancies and Substance addiction and drug abuse.

The study also determined, through interviews with the school's head teachers, that the school's environment posed a number of obstacles that contributed to the students' poor performance, as one headteacher put it;

In my school, the majority of students begin smoking and engaging in premarital sexual activity at a young age, which lowers their performance and leads to repetition. I have attempted to counsel the majority of my students with their teachers, but owing to negative influences at home and among their peers, they are unwilling to change. I believe there is a substantial societal influence on the students. Therefore, repetition enables our school to send out certain students with successful KCPE results. (HT 17)

One head teacher of a primary school expressed worry that the lack of sufficient teachers in their school, as opposed to poor delivery by teachers as always perceived by many, and the continual increase in new admissions had severely threatened their work by increasing their workload and pupil-to-teacher ratio, consequently hindering attention to slow-learning students in connection to the topics to be addressed. One primary school teacher cited student absence as a major factor in repetition, since absentees often fail to make up for lost ground once they return to class.

Further interviews with CSOs corroborated the concerns of the head teachers, who stated that the lack of parental guidance in rural areas is causing students to exhibit deviant vices that are harming their academic performance. As one stated again;

Due to poor parenting in most rural regions, it is difficult for schools to implement the no-repetition policy; as a result, student performance is declining. I have attempted to persuade schools in my region to avoid requiring students to repeat, but it gets difficult when the majority of students in a class fail to achieve a mean mark of 40%. (CSO 1)

In addition, the study determined the learners' perspectives on the causes of school repetition and its impact on academic achievement.

Table 4: Learners' responses on causes of repetition in schools.

Causes of repetition.	Strongly agreed.		Agreed.		Undecided.		Disagree.		Strongly disagree.	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Due to parents' advice.	19	14.9%	15	11.8%	3232	25.1%	28	22.0%	33	25.95%
Lack of textbooks.	67	53.1%	31	24.4%	4	3.1%	7	5.5%	18	14.17%
Failure to reach cut marks.	111	88.0%	14	11.02%	2	1.57%				
Due to failure to do exams.	79	62.2%	41	32.2%	7	5.5%				
Due to pregnancies.	5	3.93%	15	11.81%	19	14.9%	24	18.8%	64	50.3%
Due to absenteeism.	102	80.3%	19	14.96%	2	1.5%	4	3.1%		
Due to lack of parental care and support.	72	56.6%	21	16.5%	18	14.1%	4	3.1%	12	9.4%
Poor teaching techniques.	105	82.6%	14	11.02%	_	_	3	2.3%	5	3.93%

The importance of this data to the study was to establish the opinions of the learners on causes of the repetition. The effects in qualitative form to establish the academic performance as per the causes was also conducted and the data was the same as that of quantitative data. Like at one primary school most of the students that repeat cited Poor teaching techniques, Due to absenteeism, Due to advice, Failure to reach cut marks as the major contributors of repetition as opposed to Due to lack of parental care and support, Due to pregnancies, Due to failure to do exams, Due to parents' advice and Lack of textbooks. One pupil from a Primary school told me that no student has ever repeated class due to young age but majority repeat due to advice to do so from parents and guardians with intentions to improve their score.

Further interview with CSOs confirmed the sentiments of the head teachers that most repetitions were due to early pregnancies and frequent absenteeism as was maintained by one officer;

The rate of teenage pregnancies among learners in primary schools has increased in the recent past. I have been forced to talk to head teachers in my Zone to look for girls who have dropped out of school and bring them back to repeat the classes and to continue with their studies. Apart from girls there are also absenteeism among boy child in primary schools due to child labour which they cherish than their education (CSO. 2)

From table 4.6, learners' responses on the causes of repetition in schools' contrasts and agrees with that of the head teachers, class teachers, CSOs and SCDE in almost equal measures. Like head teachers, a greater percentage of learners concur that absenteeism (80%) and failure to reach cut marks (88%) are some of the main causes of repetition and hence majority strongly agree.

Of concern are the learners 100% strongly agreeing they repeated due to teachers' advice with only 14% strongly agreeing to have repeated due to parents' advice? Again, of concern are many learners (82%) strongly agreeing that they repeated due to poor teaching methods employed by teachers? This is of concern considering that many of the teachers in the study are employed by Teachers Service Commission and (80.76%) have attained a diploma and above qualifications. Again, majority of learners (74%) strongly disagreed that they repeated due to young age just like 50% strongly disagreed that they due to early pregnancies.

In summary, majority of learners agreed on the following to be reasons for repetition in their school; teachers' advice (100%), poor teaching techniques (93.6%) failure to reach cut marks (99%) absenteeism (95.2%), failure to do exams (94.2%) lack of textbooks and other learning materials (77.5%) and lack of parental care and support (72%). Again equal percentage of learners seems to be undecided (25.1%), and strongly disagree (25.90%) on whether learners repeat due to parents' advice. However, 26.7% agree that parents' advice can make learners to repeat.

4. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of the findings.

The background in which the study was done is described in the first chapter. It examines the impact of repetition on academic attainment in Kenya's state primary schools. The issue description states that the study's objective is to determine whether or not repetition has a negative or positive impact on student performance in Kenya's public primary schools. This was also the goal of the research that was presented in the chapter. This study set out to answer several issues and concerns about the impact of repetition on student engagement, the cost of repetition to primary schools in Siaya Sub County, and the methods currently being used to end the practice. The latter part of this chapter discusses the significance, scope, limitations, and hypotheses of the research as well as operational definitions of terms.

A summary of the study-related literature is provided in Chapter 2. The literature study examined topics such as how repetition affects students' performance in class, how repetition affects primary school resources, and measures used to lessen repetition in classrooms. The study's methodology was covered in Chapter 3. The research design, location of study, study population, sampling techniques, and sample size were all covered in this chapter. The chapter also included explanations of the research tools utilized, a pilot study, and metrics for measuring the validity and reliability of testing tools. In this chapter, the procedures for data collecting and analysis were also covered. The fourth part involves data analysis, while the fifth chapter presents the study's findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

Conclusion

The study found that repetition was more prevalent in seventh grade and had an impact on the academic performance of primary school students in Alego Usonga Sub County.

The goal of this research was to determine how students in Alego Usonga Sub County, Siaya County, in Kenya would fare academically after repeating the same class. According to the study, the main effects of class repetition on academic performance were stigmatization, low self-esteem, crowded classes, students who were over the age limit, suicide, and a high teacher to student ratio, all of which had a detrimental influence on students' performance in Alego Usonga Sub County.

Ninety percent of respondents said that students' low self-esteem was an excuse for failing, and 86 percent said that students' inability to articulate their thoughts and feelings was a major factor in their academic underachievement and subsequent

need to retake curricula. It was also concluded that students in the Alego Usonga sub county who scored low academically exhibited characteristics of low self-esteem, such as a submissive tone, bad body language, and a lack of confidence in themselves.

Eighty percent of respondents said that students with low academic accomplishment felt stigmatized and undervalued in the school environment, and seventy-five percent of those students reported being severely depressed as a result of their identity crisis, which only served to further hinder their performance. According to 86% of the respondents, students from disadvantaged backgrounds constantly worry about whether they will fit in academically in a competitive setting, which hurts their performance. Concerning class congestion as a result of increased enrollment and repeats, 95% of respondents were of the opinion that classes contained a large number of students who did not receive appropriate attention from their teachers, resulting in low reading scores and poor academic achievement. The majority of respondents said that a high teacher-to-student ratio impeded teachers from covering the curriculum, resulting in less cognitive engagement among students. Eighty percent of respondents stated that classroom congestion restricted students from obtaining learning materials, such as books, further harming their academic performance due to class repetition.

Repetition had an effect on the age of the student, as the survey revealed that the majority of students were slipping behind due to boredom with long school years, and 54% of respondents indicated that students who had repeated class were overaged. The overaged students performed poorly because they exhibited poor concentration during learning activities, lacked self-control, and bullied other students during group activities. These behaviors negatively impacted the teaching and learning process for the entire class. Since overage students' low performance forced class repetition, the students became dissatisfied with their education, and some decided to quit school.

Finally, school rankings revealed pervasive underachievement in majority of the elementary schools represented in the Alego Usonga Sub County sample. Sixty percent of the schools surveyed said that eliminating repetition and raising student accomplishment can be achieved by a combination of better teacher pedagogy, counseling and guidance services for students and instructors, intrinsic and extrinsic teacher learner motivation, enhanced technology in the classroom, enhanced infrastructure and other learning resources, efficient use of class time, and better scheduling. rates. Several individuals also reported reasonably smooth transition rates.

Recommendations

The Ministry of Education should take the mandate to enforce the already established government policies on grade repetition. This recommendation can however be achieved when the government primarily conduct a nationwide study aimed at ascertaining the extent to which the implementation of the policies has been done. The government should put in place policy interventions to enhance the implementation of these policies.

Recommendations for Further Studies

A study focusing on the positive effects of repetition should be conducted in primary schools

REFERENCES

- [1] Abuya, B. A., & Ngware, M. (2016). Reflections of Teachers in the FPE Era: Evidence From Six Urban Sites in Kenya. *SAGE Open*, 6(1), 2158244016629189. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244016629189>
- [2] Achoka, J. S. K. (2007). Kenya's management of secondary school education in the twenty first century: New model for excellence. *Journal of Science Technology Education and Management*, 1(2), 61–72.
- [3] Aduda, P. O., Kodero, H. M. N., & Sichari, M. (2019). The Effect of Class Repetition on the Academic Performance of Pupils in Lower Primary Schools in Homa-Bay Sub-County. *International Journal For Research In Educational Studies*, 5(9), 37–54. <https://doi.org/10.53555/es.v5i9.1126>
- [4] Ahiavi, M., & Thomas, S. (2021). TEACHERS' OPINIONS ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INCLUSIVE PROGRAMME AT ODUKPONG KPEHE CLUSTER OF SCHOOLS IN AWUTU SENYA EAST MUNICIPALITY. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 9(2).
- [5] Alarcon, G., Eschleman, K. J., & Bowling, N. A. (2009). Relationships between personality variables and burnout: A meta-analysis. *Work & Stress*, 23(3), 244–263.

- [6] Alexander, K. L., Entwisle, D., & Kabbani, N. (2003). *Grade Retention, Social Promotion, and 'Third Way'*. 29.
- [7] Al-Zoubi, S. M., & Younes, M. A. B. (2015). Low academic achievement: Causes and results. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 5(11), 2262.
- [8] Anderson, G. E., Jimerson, S. R., & Whipple, A. D. (2005). Student ratings of stressful experiences at home and school: Loss of a parent and grade retention as superlative stressors. *Journal of Applied School Psychology*, 21(1), 1–20.
- [9] Artino, A. R. (2012). Academic self-efficacy: From educational theory to instructional practice. *Perspectives on Medical Education*, 1(2), 76–85.
- [10] Aud, S., Hussar, W., Johnson, F., Kena, G., Roth, E., Manning, E., Wang, X., & Zhang, J. (2012). The Condition of Education 2012. NCES 2012-045. *National Center for Education Statistics*.
- [11] Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84(2), 191.
- [12] Bandura, A. (2018). Toward a psychology of human agency: Pathways and reflections. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 13(2), 130–136.
- [13] Bandura, A., & Hall, P. (2018). Albert bandura and social learning theory. *Learning Theories for Early Years Practice*, 63.
- [14] Bashir, S., Lockheed, M., Ninan, E., & Tan, J.-P. (2018). *Facing forward: Schooling for learning in Africa*. World Bank Publications.
- [15] BASIC EDUCATION ACT, (2013). http://www.kenyalaw.org/lex/actview.xhtml?actid=No.%2014%20of%202013#att_2
- [16] Berl, P. S. (2005). Mature teachers matter. *EXCHANGE-EXCHANGE PRESS-*, 165, 10.
- [17] Bettencourt, A., Gross, D., & Ho, G. (2016). The Costly Consequences of Not Being Socially and Behaviorally Ready by Kindergarten: Associations with Grade Retention, Receipt of Academic Support Services, and Suspensions/Expulsions. *Baltimore Education Research Consortium*.
- [18] Bii, T. C. (2014). *Influence of repetition on academic performance of pupils: A case of primary schools in Turbo Division, Uasin-Gishu County, Kenya*. 67.
- [19] Blackman, S. N. (2022). *Equitable Education for Marginalized Youth in Latin America and the Caribbean—Google Books*. https://books.google.co.ke/books?hl=en&lr=&id=TiJ4EAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PT9&dq=Brazil+for+example,+repetition+rate+in+primary+school+are+in+order+of+20%25+Nicaragua,+Peru+and+Uruguay+follow+with+repetition+rates+between+8%25+and+10%25.+&ots=YLad8kvJt6&sig=ILNMa6_aLApOZ48MZNjR2K6rXg&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false
- [20] Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101.
- [21] Brophy, J. (2006). Grade repetition Education policy series 6. *International Academic of Education & International Institute for Educational Planning*.
- [22] Burke, A. (2019). Student retention models in higher education: A literature review. *College and University*, 94(2), 12–21.
- [23] Cameron, L., Seager, J., & Shah, M. (2020). *Crimes against morality: Unintended consequences of criminalizing sex work* (No. 0898–2937). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- [24] Castro, F. (2003). *Speech at the ceremony to launch the 2003-2004 | FIDEL Soldier of Ideas*. <http://www.fidelcastro.cu/en/discursos/speech-ceremony-launch-2003-2004>

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- [25] Christakis, D. A., Van Cleve, W., & Zimmerman, F. J. (2020). Estimation of US children's educational attainment and years of life lost associated with primary school closures during the coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic. *JAMA Network Open*, 3(11), e2028786–e2028786.
- [26] Crahay, M. (2019). *Peut-on lutter contre l'échec scolaire?* De Boeck Supérieur.
- [27] Creswell, J. W. (2002). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative* (Vol. 7). Prentice Hall Upper Saddle River, NJ.
- [28] Crouch, E., Probst, J. C., Radcliff, E., Bennett, K. J., & McKinney, S. H. (2019). Prevalence of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) among US children. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 92, 209–218.
- [29] Dahir, C. A., Cinotti, D. A., & Feirsen, R. (2019). Beyond compliance: Assessing administrators' commitment to comprehensive school counseling. *NASSP Bulletin*, 103(2), 118–138.
- [30] Day, L. J. (2018). A gross anatomy flipped classroom effects performance, retention, and higher-level thinking in lower performing students. *Anatomical Sciences Education*, 11(6), 565–574.
- [31] De Talancé, M., Ferry, M., & Nino-Zarazúa, M. (2019). *Did Debt Relief Initiatives help to reach the MDGs? A Focus on Primary Education*. Erudite.
- [32] Department of Education. (2005). *Department of Education Annual Report*. 166.
- [33] Di Gropello, E. (2006). *Meeting the challenges of secondary education in Latin America and East Asia: Improving efficiency and resource mobilization*. World Bank Publications.
- [34] Dong, Y. (2010). Kept back to get ahead? Kindergarten retention and academic performance. *European Economic Review*, 54(2), 219–236.
- [35] Dovigo, F. (2015). *The Kenyan and Italian lower secondary schools: A comparative analysis of the variations in the quality of education in the sixth grade level*.
- [36] Dziurzyński, K., & Duda, E. (2018). Grade repetition as a consequence of school failures. *Journal of Modern Science*, 38(3), 133–148. <https://doi.org/10.13166/jms/95080>
- [37] Eide, E. R., & Showalter, M. H. (2001). The effect of grade retention on educational and labor market outcomes. *Economics of Education Review*, 20(6), 563–576.
- [38] Eskin, M., Sun, J.-M., Abuidhail, J., Yoshimasu, K., Kujan, O., Janghorbani, M., Flood, C., Carta, M. G., Tran, U. S., & Mechri, A. (2016). Suicidal behavior and psychological distress in university students: A 12-nation study. *Archives of Suicide Research*, 20(3), 369–388.
- [39] Feirsen, R., Dahir, C., & Cinotti, D. (2021). Moving from School Counseling Compliance to Cohesion: Making Mandates Meaningful. *Journal of School Counseling*, 19(25), n25.
- [40] Fiszbein, A., & Stanton, S. (2018). *The future of education in Latin America and the caribbean: Possibilities for United States investment and engagement*.
- [41] Gathura, F., Momanyi, M., & Mwalw'a, S. (2021). Effectiveness of Students' Council Leaders Involvement in Management Roles for Enhancing Students' Discipline among Different Categories of Public Secondary Schools in Machakos County, Kenya. *Journal of African Interdisciplinary Studies*, 5(7), 89–116.
- [42] GATWIRI, J. (2013). *FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO BOYS'DROP OUT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN MUTHAMBI DIVISION, THARAKA NITHI COUNTY, KENYA*.
- [43] Geoffrey E. Mills, L. R. G. (2016). *EDUCATIONAL Research: Competencies for Analysis and Applications*. Pearson Education Limited.
- [44] Glick, P., & Sahn, D. E. (2012). Early academic performance, grade repetition, and school attainment in Senegal. *World Bank Economic Review*.

- [45] Gray, D. E. (2013). *Doing Research in the Real World*. <https://www.amazon.co.uk/Doing-Research-Real-World-David/dp/1446295311>
- [46] Gustafsson, M. (2018). *Standardised testing and examinations at the primary level Current thinking and practices*.
- [47] Hargreaves, D. H. (2001). A capital theory of school effectiveness and improvement [1]. *British Educational Research Journal*, 27(4), 487–503.
- [48] Holzinger, L. A., & Biddle, N. (2019). The relationship between child labour, participation in cultural activities and the schooling outcomes of children: An analysis by Indigenous status. In *Routledge Handbook of Indigenous Wellbeing*. Routledge.
- [49] Huddleston, A. P. (2014). Achievement at Whose Expense? A Literature Review of Test-Based Grade Retention Policies in US Schools. *Education Policy Analysis Archives/Archivos Analíticos de Políticas Educativas*, 22, 1–31.
- [50] Hughes, J. N., Kwok, O.-M., & Im, M. H. (2013). Effect of retention in first grade on parents' educational expectations and children's academic outcomes. *American Educational Research Journal*, 50(6), 1336–1359.
- [51] Hughes, J. N., West, S. G., Kim, H., & Bauer, S. S. (2018). Effect of early grade retention on school completion: A prospective study. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 110(7), 974.
- [52] Hungi, N. (2011). Characteristics of school heads and their schools. *Sacmeq*, 3, 1–38.
- [53] Ikeda, M. (2011). PISA in focus: When students repeat grades or are transferred out of school: What does it mean for education systems. Available at the OECD: [Http://Www. Oecd. Org/Dataoecd/35/58/48363440. Pdf](http://www.Oecd.Org/Dataoecd/35/58/48363440.Pdf).
- [54] Jacob, B. A., & Lefgren, L. (2004). Remedial education and student achievement: A regression-discontinuity analysis. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 86(1), 226–244.
- [55] Jimerson, S. R., & Ferguson, P. (2007). A longitudinal study of grade retention: Academic and behavioral outcomes of retained students through adolescence. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 22(3), 314.
- [56] Kaliannan, M., & Chandran, S. D. (2012). Empowering students through outcome-based education (OBE). *Research in Education*, 87(1), 50–63.
- [57] KARIUKI, K. I. (2018). *ADEQUACY OF TEACHER CHARACTERISTICS, CLASSROOM FACILITIES AND MATERIALS ASSOCIATED WITH QUALITY EARLY CHILDHOOD DEVELOPMENT AND EDUCATION IN NAKURU COUNTY, KENYA*.
- [58] Kattan, R. B., & Székely, M. (2015). Analyzing the dynamics of school dropout in upper secondary education in Latin America: A cohort approach. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, 7223.
- [59] Kika, J., & Kotze, J. (2019). *Unpacking grade repetition patterns in light of the progression policy in the Further Education and Training phase*.
- [60] King, H. S. (2019). *Qualitative Analysis of Adult Perceptions of Their K-12 Grade Retention*. Gardner-Webb University.
- [61] Kipngetch, S. N. (2019a). *Fundamental Issues in Implementation of Government Policy on Class Repetition in Basic Education in Kenya*.
- [62] Kipngetch, S. N. (2019b). *Fundamental Issues in Implementation of Government Policy on Class Repetition in Basic Education in Kenya*.
- [63] Kipngetch, S. N., Chumba, S., & Tanui, J. (2017). Head teachers' transformational leadership intervention strategies on class repetition in primary school education in Kenya. *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(5), 348–356.
- [64] Koros, P. K., Sang, A. K., & Bosire, J. N. (2013). *Repetition rates in public secondary schools in Kericho District in relation to selected school characteristics. A situational analysis*.

- [65] Kraft, M. A. (2020). Interpreting effect sizes of education interventions. *Educational Researcher*, 49(4), 241–253.
- [66] Kyereko, D. O., Smith, W. C., Hlovor, I., & Keney, G. (2022). Understanding grade repetition from the perspectives of teachers and principals in basic schools in Ghana. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 93, 102633.
- [67] Lane, J., & Lane, A. (2001). SELF-EFFICACY AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE. *Social Behavior and Personality: An International Journal*, 29(7), 687–693. <https://doi.org/10.2224/sbp.2001.29.7.687>
- [68] Lauwerier, T., & Akkari, A. (2015). Teachers and the quality of basic education in sub-Saharan Africa. *Education Research and Foresight: Working Papers Series*, 11.
- [69] Lavy, V., Silva, O., & Weinhardt, F. (2012). The good, the bad, and the average: Evidence on ability peer effects in schools. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 30(2), 367–414.
- [70] Liu, H., Ke, W., Chen, H., Liang, C., & Yang, L. (2022). The perceptions of sexuality and sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) among adolescent STD patients: A qualitative study. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*.
- [71] Liu, X., Ping, S., & Gao, W. (2019). Changes in undergraduate students' psychological well-being as they experience university life. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(16), 2864.
- [72] Mackatiani, C. I., Ariemba, A. N., & Ngware, J. W. (2020). African response to quality education: Comparative perspectives on quality primary education in Kenya. *European Journal of Education Studies*.
- [73] Manacorda, M. (2012). The cost of grade retention. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 94(2), 596–606.
- [74] Mattingly, M. J., & Schaefer, A. (2021). Education in rural America: Challenges and opportunities. *Serving Gifted Students in Rural Settings*, 53–70.
- [75] Mbunde, J. M. (2017). Head Teachers' Role in Facilitating School Facilities that Influence Pupils' Performance in Kcpe. *European Scientific Journal*, 13(19), 146–155.
- [76] Millea, M., Wills, R., Elder, A., & Molina, D. (2018). What matters in college student success? Determinants of college retention and graduation rates. *Education*, 138(4), 309–322.
- [77] Mills, G. E., & Gay, L. R. (2019). *Educational research: Competencies for analysis and applications*. ERIC.
- [78] Mudemb, E. V. (2013). *Causes of dropout among boys and girls from secondary schools in Ugenya district, Siaya County, Kenya*.
- [79] Mugenda, A. G. (2008). *Social Science Research: Theory and Principles*. Applied Research and Training Services.
- [80] Mugenda, O. M., & Mugenda, A. (2003). *Research methods: Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*. Nairobi: African Centre for Technology Studies.
- [81] Murithi, T. (2006). African approaches to building peace and social solidarity. *African Journal on Conflict Resolution*, 6(2), 9–33.
- [82] Musasia, A. M., Nakhanu, S. B., & Wekesa, W. D. (2012). *Investigation of factors that influence syllabus coverage in secondary school mathematics in Kenya*.
- [83] Mutai, C. C. (2016). Gender differences in mathematics performance among secondary school students in Bureti sub-county, Kericho County Kenya. *Unpublished Master's Thesis*. Kenyatta University, Kenya. Retrieved from [Http://ir.library.ku.ac.ke/bitstream/Handle/123456789/14968/Gender%20differences%20in%20mathematics%20performance.Pdf](http://ir.library.ku.ac.ke/bitstream/Handle/123456789/14968/Gender%20differences%20in%20mathematics%20performance.Pdf).
- [84] Mwenda, K. K., & Muuka, G. N. (2009). *The Challenge of Change in Africa's Higher Education in the 21st Century*. <https://www.cambriapress.com/pub.cfm?bid=303>
- [85] Ndaruhutse, S., Branelly, L., Latham, M., & Penson, J. (2008). *Grade repetition in primary schools in Sub-Saharan Africa: An evidence base for change*.

- [86] Ndiwewo, P. O., Aloka, P. J., & Raburu, P. A. (2016). *Influence of learner involvement on academic performance of secondary school students in Kenya*.
- [87] Ngari, E. M. (2020). Influence of School Strategies on Internal Efficiency in Constituency Funded Day Secondary Schools in Nairobi, Kenya. *African Educational Research Journal*, 8(4), 649–663.
- [88] Ngware, M. (2013). *Quality and access to education in urban informal settlements in Kenya*.
- [89] Ning, B. (2020). *School Climate Matters: Shanghai Schools from a Comparative Perspective*. Routledge.
- [90] Njeng'ere, D. (2014). *The role of curriculum in fostering national cohesion and integration: Opportunities and challenges*.
- [91] OECD. (2012). *Equity and Quality in Education: Supporting Disadvantaged Students and Schools*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264130852-en>
- [92] Onyango, D. O. (2020). *Perception of School Heads on Teachers' Professionalism and Pupils' Behavior as Determinants of Academic Achievement among Primary Schools in Central Nyanza, Kenya | East African Journal of Education and Social Sciences*. <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/eajess/article/view/218630>
- [93] Orodho, B., Ajanga, I., Jones, P., & Mudavadi, P. (2005). *A new napier grass stunting disease in Kenya associated with phytoplasma*. 313.
- [94] Orodho, J. A. (2009). Elements of education and social science research methods. *Nairobi/Maseno*, 2(6), 26–133.
- [95] Orodho, J. A., Waweru, P. N., Ndichu, M., & Nthinguri, R. (2013). Basic education in Kenya: Focus on strategies applied to cope with school-based challenges inhibiting effective implementation of curriculum. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1(11), 1–20.
- [96] Osei, G. M. (2006). Teachers in Ghana: Issues of training, remuneration and effectiveness. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 26(1), 38–51.
- [97] Pagani, L., Argentin, G., Gui, M., & Stanca, L. (2016). The impact of digital skills on educational outcomes: Evidence from performance tests. *Educational Studies*, 42(2), 137–162.
- [98] Phan, H. P., Ngu, B. H., Wang, H.-W., Shih, J.-H., Shi, S.-Y., & Lin, R.-Y. (2018). Understanding levels of best practice: An empirical validation. *PLoS One*, 13(6), e0198888.
- [99] Plano Clark, V. L., Huddleston-Casas, C. A., Churchill, S. L., O'Neil Green, D., & Garrett, A. L. (2008). Mixed methods approaches in family science research. *Journal of Family Issues*, 29(11), 1543–1566.
- [100] Rhodes, J., Thomas, J. M., & Liles, A. R. (2018). Predictors of Grade Retention among Children in an Elementary School Truancy Intervention. *Journal of At-Risk Issues*, 21(1), 1–10.
- [101] Rivera, I. (2022). Education, Health Care, and Poverty in Cuba. *Perspectives on Global Development and Technology*, 20(5–6), 551–557.
- [102] Rodríguez Rodríguez, D. (2022). Grade retention, academic performance and motivational variables in Compulsory Secondary Education: A longitudinal study. *Psicothema*.
- [103] Sekiwu, D., Ssempala, F., & Frances, N. (2020). Investigating the Relationship between School Attendance and Academic Performance in Universal Primary Education: The Case of Uganda. *African Educational Research Journal*, 8(2), 152–160.
- [104] Sharma, U., Forlin, C., & Loreman, T. (2008). Impact of training on pre-service teachers' attitudes and concerns about inclusive education and sentiments about persons with disabilities. *Disability & Society*, 23(7), 773–785.
- [105] Shrestha, U., Williams, T., Al, S., Alies, S., Geldermalsen, V., & Zaidi, A. (2019). *What is the relationship between politics, education reforms, and learning? Evidence from a new database and nine case studies*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25279.05286>

- [106] Simmons, J., & Alexander, L. (1975). *The Determinants of School Achievement in Developing Countries: A Review of the Research*.
- [107] Snyder, T. D., & Dillow, S. A. (2010). Digest of Education Statistics, 2009. NCES 2010-013. *National Center for Education Statistics*.
- [108] Tani, M. C. (2018). The effective implementation of the policy of automatic class promotion in Cameroon public primary schools: The case of North west and South west regions. *Bulgarian Journal of Science and Education Policy*, 12(1), 63–100.
- [109] Taylor, S. (2008). Taylor, S. (2008) Thinking of research supervision as a form of teaching. *Research Supervision: An Online Journal*.
- [110] Thomas, L. (2012). Building student engagement and belonging in Higher Education at a time of change. *Paul Hamlyn Foundation*, 100(1–99).
- [111] Uchihara, T., Webb, S., & Yanagisawa, A. (2019). The effects of repetition on incidental vocabulary learning: A meta-analysis of correlational studies. *Language Learning*, 69(3), 559–599.
- [112] UNESCO. (2012). *2012 / Global Education Monitoring Report*. <https://en.unesco.org/gem-report/taxonomy/term/202>
- [113] UNESCO. (2018, October 9). SDG Resources for Educators—Quality Education. *UNESCO*. <https://en.unesco.org/themes/education/sdgs/material/04>
- [114] UNESCO. (2021). UNESCO 2021 World Conference on Education for Sustainable Development. *UNESCO*. <https://en.unesco.org/events/ESDfor2030>
- [115] Valbuena, J., Mediavilla, M., Choi, Á., & Gil, M. (2021). Effects of grade retention policies: A literature review of empirical studies applying causal inference. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 35(2), 408–451.
- [116] Van Canegem, T., Van Houtte, M., & Demanet, J. (2021). Grade retention and academic self-concept: A multilevel analysis of the effects of schools' retention composition. *British Educational Research Journal*, 47(5), 1340–1360.
- [117] Ward, P. M., & Wilson, R. H. (2018). *Latin America's Future Public Policy Challenges: A Ten-year Time Horizon—Ward—2018—Latin American Policy* -. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/lamp.12150>
- [118] Wilkenson, A. M. (1991). *Scientist's Handbook for Writing Papers and Dissertations (PRENTICE HALL ADVANCED REFERENCE SERIES PHYSICAL AND LIFE SCIENCES)*. <https://www.amazon.com/Scientists-Handbook-Dissertations-RENTICE-REFERENCE/dp/0139694110>
- [119] World Bank. (1997). *World development report 1997: The state in a changing world*. The World Bank.
- [120] Xia, N., & Kirby, S. N. (2009). *Retaining Students in Grade: A Literature Review of the Effects of Retention on Students' Academic and Nonacademic Outcomes*. RAND Corporation. https://www.rand.org/pubs/technical_reports/TR678.html
- [121] Yang, M.-Y., Chen, Z., Rhodes, J. L., & Orooji, M. (2018). A longitudinal study on risk factors of grade retention among elementary school students using a multilevel analysis: Focusing on material hardship and lack of school engagement. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 88, 25–32.
- [122] Yang, Q., Tian, L., Huebner, E. S., & Zhu, X. (2019). Relations among academic achievement, self-esteem, and subjective well-being in school among elementary school students: A longitudinal mediation model. *School Psychology*, 34(3), 328–340. <https://doi.org/10.1037/spq0000292>
- [123] Yaylı, S. K. (2019). *A Reflective Study on EFL Instructors' Dropping Out Stories through the Lens of Motivation and Self*.